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The Indispensability of Celebrity on Consumer's Purchasing Behaviour in the Brewery Industry in Cameroon

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Abstract

The modern marketing environment has introduced a new paradigm for advertising referred to as celebrity endorsements. These forms of advertising influence consumers' pre-purchase attitudes and draw attention to a product. This study consequently sought to assess the effect of celebrity endorsement on customers' buying behaviour in the soft drink industry. Specifically the study purport to investigate the effect of (a) celebrity match (b) celebrity attractiveness (c) celebrity credibility and (d) celebrity previous endorsement on consumer buying behaviour. To accomplish these objectives, data was sourced from customers of brewery's products using simple random sampling technique. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, correlative research design and inferential statistics. The research findings revealed that celebrity endorsement has a positive and significant effect on consumer's buying behaviour in the soft drink industry as indicated by the adjusted R-squared of 0.798. This suggest that 79.8% variation in consumer buying behaviour is explained by celebrity match, celebrity attractiveness, celebrity Credibility and Celebrity previous endorsement at 1% level of significance. Since celebrity endorsement has a significant role on consumer's buying behaviour in the soft drink industry, we recommend that advertisers should match the celebrity credibility, celebrity attractiveness and celebrity previous endorsement by choosing, and shaping the celebrity to match with the target market expectations.

Keywords: Celebrity Endorsement, Consumer Buying Behaviour, Celebrity Match and Celebrity Previous Endorsement

1. Introduction

New events and innovations with particular qualities and characteristics have entered human life since the invention of the internet. People's lives have undergone tremendous change as a result of e-commerce, mobile commerce, and modern social media and mobile marketing. Celebrity endorsements have long been a common marketing tactic; they are now acknowledged as a significant and pervasive phenomenon of contemporary marketing as well as a practical marketing communication approach according to Schimmelpfennig (2019).

Modern society has a tendency to ignore all advertisements, whether they appear on television, in magazines, or in newspapers. Despite that, it's impossible to dismiss the appeal of a celebrity. In order to keep clients interested in the brand, the use of a celebrity in an advertisement is one of the finest tactics. Celebrities have a stronger influence on people because of how attractive they are and how talented they are. McCracken (1989) asserts that, more than any other group in society; young people are impacted by celebrities. When young individuals are exposed to celebrities in the media, they frequently establish secondary attachments to them, which are crucial for the formation of an adult identity as they transition into adulthood (Boon & Lomore, 2001). Since they serve as a model for young people as they develop their beliefs, attitudes, and behavior, marketers have discovered that celebrities may be a potent tool to influence and respond to young consumers' behavior. Consequently, the majority of celebrity-endorsed advertisements in all their forms mostly appeal to the younger demographic (Run *et al.*, 2010).

It is notable that not all the celebrities prove to be successful endorsers, this makes the selection process quite difficult. Hence, advertisers must carefully select celebrities they use so that in the event where any micro aspect goes wrong in celebrity endorsement selection process, the celebrity endorsed advertisement campaign will not be effective. According to Ahmed *et al.* (2012) advertisers need to take more caution and understand the market before choosing a celebrity that will endorse their products.

Several businesses in England have been claiming to be "by appointment to the Queen" for hundreds of years in order to indicate that they are supported by the British royal family. When a well-known person recommends a product, consumers are frequently lured in by the notion that by buying the product, they are also endorsing the product and the famous person (Lascu & Zinkhan, 1999).

In Africa, and precisely in Nigeria, celebrity endorsement has become a common exercise for advertisers and product owners. Ekeh (2019) suggested a sharp switch in Nigeria from sales promotion strategy to celebrity endorsements by businesses, he asserted that the fight to control the Nigerian market has grown tougher with over time, and brand owners are deploying various marketing strategies in a bid to dominate the market. Understanding how customers will react to various strategies employed to achieve their goal is one of the problems that organizations face in the business world today. Consequently, marketers are now interested in researching consumer behavior. The main objective of celebrity endorsement is to influence consumers' purchasing decisions; however, this power over a brand is usually altered or amplified by consumers' recollections. Associative connections to the brand name in the minds of consumers help to create memories of it. These brand perceptions impact decisions about consideration, assessment, and ultimately purchases. Thus, if celebrity endorsement is a means to an end, does it really influence consumers' purchase decisions about a product? Many research studies have been conducted at the international level to answer this question about consumers' attitudes toward products as a result of celebrities used in advertising such products. To this end, this study attempts to make several contributions to the body of actionable knowledge on the effect of endorsement on consumers' behavior in the brewery industry in Cameroon. In this light the major objective of the study is to examine the effect of celebrity endorsement on consumer buying behavior in brewery industry in Cameroon. Specifically the study seeks to: (a) analyse the effect of celebrity match on consumer behaviour (b) Assess the effect of celebrity attractiveness on consumer behaviour (c) Investigate effect of celebrity Credibility on consumer behaviour and (d)Examine the effect of celebrity previous endorsement and consumer behaviour.

2. Literature Review

As concerns the conceptual clarification, Khatri (2006) holds that "celebrities" are people who enjoy public recognition and possess such attributes as attractiveness and trustworthiness. Celebrities are well-known and well-liked individuals who have excelled in their respective fields of endeavor and thus command respect, acceptance, popularity, and followership in society. According to Jo Onewo *et al.* (2013), celebrities are distinguished from ordinary people by a number of qualities. Popularity, great social or cultural recognition, attention-getting ability, and fame within their own faculties are some of these qualities. Marketers often use celebrity endorsements as a successful tactic. From a psychological perspective, it responds to consumer needs. Consequently, it affects his behavior and decision-making in relation to the promoted good or brand (Khatri, 2006).

According to Erdogan & Baker (2000) a celebrity's endorsement adds glitz to a product and raises the possibility that, in a crowded market, a well-known face will boost appeal and name recognition. Businesses invest a lot of money on celebrities to promote their goods or sponsored messages on traditional and electronic media in the hopes that this will encourage favorable views toward the brand and, in turn, increase sales and profits by raising consumers' preference for the brand.

Kotler and Keller (2007) defines consumer behavior as the study of people, groups, or organisations and the methods they employ to choose, secure, utilise, and discard goods, experiences, or ideas in order to meet wants, as well as the effects these methods have on the consumer and society. The study of how, what, when, and why people buy is another definition of consumer behaviour. It describes the purchasing process that everyone who is willing to purchase, including households, groups, or organisations, goes through (Kotler, 2011). Some of the most common stimuli are personal factors, cultural factors and social factors. In addition, the consumer's personal factors such as perception, motivation, learning and memory comprise an influence on how the consumer responds to the marketing stimuli (Kotler and Keller, 2007).

As concern empirical literature, few studies have been carried out with the aimed being to investigate the effect of celebrity endorsement on customer buying behavior. Interested in the effect of celebrity endorsement on purchase intention, Widarto and Anindita (2018) reveal that celebrity endorsement has a positive impact on purchase intention, and the three dimensions namely trustworthiness, attractiveness, and expertise play an important role on forming celebrity endorsement variable. Moreover, trustworthiness of the celebrity is the biggest contributor on celebrity endorsement variable which is followed by attractiveness and expertise dimensions.

Wenny and Sabrina (2016) examined comparing the use of famous endorser and lay endorser in predicting consumer intention to buy in the Indonesian context. This research compared the use of famous endorser and lay endorser in advertisements in predicting consumer intention in buying a consumer goods product. A total of two hundred and ninety (290) undergraduate students participated in this study. The data was then analyzed using structural equation modeling. The results show that the use of famous endorser in product advertisement is more effective than the use of lay endorser.

In the same light, Novita (2020), examined the impact of celebrity endorsements on consumers' purchase intention in Indian. The population of the study included three hundred and thirty-six (336) Indian respondents who are exposed to celebrity endorsements for various brands. The study considers three attributes of celebrity endorsements as suggested by Ohanian (1990) attractiveness, trustworthiness and expertise. However, the beta coefficients reveal a low degree of correlation between celebrity endorsements and purchase intention. Further, attractiveness and trustworthiness are found to have a significant impact on the purchase intention, while expertise did not have a significant impact on purchase intention.

3. Methodology of the Study

The research adopted is a causal research design. Causal research design is conducted to identify the extent and nature of cause-and-effect relationships between Celebrity endorsement and consumer's behaviour. The variables under study were corporate Celebrity endorsement which is the independent variable with its specific components being celebrity match, celebrity attractiveness, celebrity credibility and celebrity previous endorsement. The dependent variable is consumer's behaviour. The data for the study was obtained through questionnaires administered to customers of brewery's products. They included customers of Brassieres Du Cameroun, UCB, Guinness Cameroon, and Source Du Paye. In this study, a representative sample was drawn following Miller and Brewer (2003) formula of calculating sample size. In order to obtain the sample size we used the formula below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(a)^2} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where "N" is the sample frame, "n" the sample size and "a", the margin of error, which in our case is 5%.

Therefore, $n = \frac{172}{1+76(0.05)^2} = 120$

The econometric model is specified as follow:

$$CB = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 CE + \alpha_2 CA + \alpha_3 CM + \alpha_4 CC + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where α_0 represent the constant term, $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ and α_4 are the parameters to be estimated, ε is the error term. CE represent Celebrity endorsement; CA Celebrity attractiveness; CM Celebrity match and CC Celebrity credibility. The dependent variable which is Consumers behaviour is represented by CB. The a priori expectation of the above model is that $\alpha_0 \neq 0, \alpha_1 \geq 0, \alpha_2 \geq 0, \alpha_3 \geq 0$ and $\alpha_4 \geq 0$.

The ordinary least Square technique was used since the dependent variable was continuous and captured thought a generated index used to capture respondents purchasing behaviour. The Cronbach's alpha test was used to investigate the reliability of the instrument. The resultant Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.72 indicate an acceptable level of internal consistency.

4. Presentation of Results

4.1. Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Summary Statistics

Descriptive Statistics									
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
Celebrity Match	98	1.00	5.00	3.3469	1.46507	.224	.244	1.398	.483
Celebrity Attractiveness	98	1.00	5.00	2.0714	1.14198	1.002	.244	.146	.483
Celebrity Credibility	98	1.00	5.00	2.5306	.94383	.323	.244	.076	.483
Celebrity Endorsement Previous	98	1.00	5.00	1.3878	.89250	2.878	.244	8.219	.483
Consumer Behaviour	98	1.00	5.00	2.1224	1.20365	1.100	.244	.312	.483

Source: Constructed by authors Using Primary Data

Table 1 presents the summary statistics of the variables in the study. From the result, all the variables have a minimum value of at least 1 and a maximum value of 5. The standard deviations of the variables are relatively small, less than half of their mean, indicating that the values of these variables are clustered around the mean. The normality of the distributions is confirmed by looking at their Skewness and Kurtosis as they have Skewness less than one and Kurtosis less than three.

4.2. Presentation of Correlation Results

Table 2: Presentation of Correlation Results

	Celebrity Match	Celebrity Attractiveness	Celebrity Credibility	Celebrity Endorsement Previous	Consumer Behaviour
Celebrity Match	1				
Celebrity Attractiveness	.071	1			
Celebrity Credibility	.219*	.334**	1		
Celebrity Endorsement Previous	.280**	.426**	.402**	1	
Consumer Behaviour	.151	.390**	.333**	.474**	1

Source: Constructed by authors Using Primary Data

From the result on table 2, celebrity match is positively correlated with celebrity attractiveness, celebrity credibility and consumer behaviour. Celebrity attractiveness is also positively correlated with celebrity credibility,

celebrity previous endorsement and consumer behaviour. Celebrity credibility is positively correlated with celebrity previous endorsement and consumer behaviour. Also, celebrity previous endorsement is correlated consumer behaviour. From the result, all pairs of variables exhibit weak and moderate positive correlations between them as the correlation coefficient between the pairs of variables is less than 0.5. The correlation results can act as a prelude to test for multicollinearity. If the coefficient between the independent variables is greater than 0.8, it shows potential multicollinearity. However, from the table above, all the coefficients are less than 0.8, hence there is no problem of multicollinearity. This is further supported with the Variance Inflation Factor results below.

4.3. Test of multicollinearity

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
Celebrity Match	1.054	.949
Celebrity Attractiveness	1.452	.689
Celebrity Credibility	1.273	.784
Celebrity Previous Endorsement	1.248	.789
Consumer Behaviour	1.243	.805
Mean VIF	1.271	.

Source: Constructed by authors Using Primary Data

Table 3 shows the VIF result which is used to measure the degree of multicollinearity. If the VIF of a coefficient of a variable exceeds 2.50, then that variable is highly collinear, and multicollinearity becomes a problem (Gujarati, 2004). The VIF test for multicollinearity showed no evidence for the existence of multicollinearity since the mean VIF was 1.243 which is less than 2.50.

4.4. Verification of Hypotheses

At this stage, we are going to look at which hypothesis is to be rejected and which one is to be accepted.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.895 ^a	.801	.798	.14387

a) Predictors: (Constant), Celebrity Match, Celebrity Attractiveness, Celebrity Credibility, Celebrity Previous Endorsement

Table 4 show the R-squared which measures the joint contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable. The adjusted R-squared is 0.798. This means that 79.8% variation in consumer behaviour is explained by the independent variables in this model. The also show that the remaining 20.2% is explained by other variables not included in our model. With at least 78% contribution, we can conclude that our variables fit the model. R is the correlation coefficient which show the joint relationship between all the variables included in the model.

4.5. ANOVA Results

Table 5: ANOVA Results

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	59.841	32	1.870	90.343	.000 ^b
	Residual	.559	27	.021		
	Total	60.400	59			
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Behaviour						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Celebrity Match, Celebrity Attractiveness, Celebrity Credibility, Celebrity Previous Endorsement						

Source: Constructed by authors Using Primary Data

The Fisher's F test is used to determine the risk of rejecting the null hypothesis when it is true. From table 5, we can observe that the p-value of the F-statistics (0.000) is less than 1%, this implies the independent variables in the model (Celebrity Match, Celebrity Attractiveness, Celebrity Credibility, Celebrity Previous Endorsement) are statistically significant globally at 1% level of significance. This therefore shows that celebrity endorsement has significant effects on consumer behaviour in Soft Drink Industry in Bamenda.

4.6. Regression Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.455	.427		1.064	.290
	Celebrity Match	.126	.074	.150	1.719	.089
	Celebrity Attractiveness	.596	.093	.558	6.375	.000
	Celebrity Credibility	.283	.170	.210	1.663	.100
	Celebrity Previous Endorsement	.104	.028	.101	3.703	.001
	Gender	.270	.105	.237	2.559	.012
	Age	.192	.128	.161	1.505	.136
	Education	-.167	.124	-.131	-1.342	.183
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Behaviour						

Source: Constructed by authors Using Primary Data

This study seeks to examine the effects of celebrity endorsement on the consumer behaviour of Soft Drink Industry in Bamenda. From the results, the coefficient of celebrity match is positive, meaning the celebrity match positively affects consumer buying behaviour, indicating that celebrity match will lead to an increase in consumer behaviour. Specifically, from the result, an increase in celebrity match by 1 standard point, will lead to a 0.126 units increase in the consumer buying behaviour. This result is statistically significant at 10% level of significance since the p-value of 0.089.

The results also show that celebrity attractiveness have a positive effect on consumer behaviour in Soft Drink Industry in Bamenda. This means that a point increase in efficiency ratio, increases consumer behaviour by 0.596 units. This result is statistically significant at 1% level of significance since the p-value is 0.000. This study results corroborates with Nelson and Deborah (2017). The results also show that celebrity credibility has a positive effect on consumer behaviour as its coefficient is positive. Indicating that, an increase in celebrity credibility increases consumer buying behaviour. Specifically, a point increase in celebrity credibility will increase consumer behaviour by about 0.283units. The results contradicts ZorBari-Nwitambu and Kalu (2017) who stated that

consumer will tend to have a positive disposition towards a celebrity who is good at what they do, thereby commanding more attraction and followership.

The results also indicate that celebrity previous endorsement positively affects consumer behaviour in Soft Drink Industry in Bamenda. This implies that, increase in celebrity previous endorsement analysis increases consumer behaviour as shown by its coefficient of 0.104. Specifically, a point increase in celebrity previous endorsement analysis will increase consumer behaviour by about 0.104 units. This result is statistically significant at 1% level of significance since the p-value of 0.001. The result contradicts those of Fadeyi (2020) who found that there is no evidence proving that the usage of celebrity endorsement will achieve stronger brand loyalty in comparison to a non-use of celebrity endorsement. Nevertheless, they are in corroboration of those of Lawal (2021).

5. Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

It is believed that, advertisers and advertising agencies go to great lengths to use celebrities to endorse a variety of products in the hopes that the public image of these celebrities will trickle down to the endorsed products and lead to their adoption by target consumers. This hypothesis is supported by the present study. According to results from this study, endorsements from famous people have a favourable and considerable impact on consumers' purchasing decisions. The study demonstrates that celebrity endorsement has a greater impact on customer attitudes and intention to buy. In this regard, we came to the conclusion that Bamenda-based soft drink distributors should carefully choose the celebrity who will appear in their commercial advertisements. The study recommends that, the general public stands out as the most persuasive force when marketing to a mixed audience that includes both middle-class and low-income individuals.

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